

Rewriting Euler's Beautiful Equation with the Golden and Plastic Ratios

The mighty one.

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Abstract

Some variations on a theme by Euler, in case it is of some use to someone. Alternate versions of The Beautiful Equation, using the Golden Ratio φ and the analogous Plastic Ratio ρ .

Keywords: Euler, Beautiful Equation, Golden Ratio, Plastic Ratio.

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1 Known versions with φ or ρ

Euler's beautiful equation

$$e^{i\pi} - 1 = 0$$

can trivially be rewritten with φ as

$$e^{i\pi}\varphi - \varphi = 0$$

There are also the joke versions

$$e^{i\pi} - 1^\varphi = 0$$

shown in a video [1], or

$$e^{i\pi} - \varphi^0 = 0$$

Jackson [2] showed a more complex version,

$$e^{\frac{i\pi}{1+\varphi}} + e^{-\frac{i\pi}{1+\varphi}} + e^{\frac{i\pi}{\varphi}} + e^{-\frac{i\pi}{\varphi}} = 0$$

The usual method is the simpler

$$e^{i\pi} + \varphi^2 = \varphi$$

shown, for example, by Mansouri [3], although I saw this result online, credited to someone else but can't find it now.

Since ρ

$$\rho + 1 = \rho^3$$

is analogous to φ

$$\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2$$

we can simply drop in ρ for φ :

$$e^{i\pi} + \rho^3 = \rho$$

Hartl [4] shows how to write Euler using the circle constant τ ($= 2\pi$) instead of π , as

$$e^{i\tau} = 1$$

Which leads to the φ and ρ versions,

$$e^{i\tau} + \varphi = \varphi^2$$

and

$$e^{i\tau} + \rho = \rho^3$$

These simply switch the φ and ρ terms to the opposite sides, compared to the π versions.

2 New versions using both φ and ρ

Using the all-powerful one, we can rewrite Euler using both φ and ρ . I kept the steps separate to make it easier to follow, for those not familiar with φ algebra.

$$e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi} = -1 \tag{2}$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi} = \varphi - \varphi^2 \tag{3} \quad (\textit{The mighty one})$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi} + \varphi^2 = \varphi \tag{4}$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi}\varphi + \varphi\varphi^2 = \varphi^2 \tag{5} \quad (\textit{Sneaky move, multiply by } \varphi)$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi}\varphi + \varphi(\varphi + 1) = \varphi^2 \tag{6} \quad (\textit{Left side first})$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi}\varphi + \varphi^2 + \varphi = \varphi^2 \tag{7}$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi}\varphi + \varphi^2 + \varphi = \varphi + 1 \tag{8} \quad (\textit{Right side})$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi}\varphi + \varphi^2 + \varphi = \varphi + \rho^3 - \rho \tag{9} \quad (\textit{The mighty one})$$

$$\therefore e^{i\pi}\varphi + \varphi^2 = \rho^3 - \rho \tag{10} \quad (\textit{Subtract } \varphi)$$

$$\therefore 0 = \rho^3 - \rho - e^{i\pi}\varphi - \varphi^2 \tag{11}$$

$$\therefore \rho^3 - \varphi^2 - e^{i\pi}\varphi - \rho = 0 \tag{12} \quad (\textit{Prettyfy})$$

Alternatively,

$$\varphi^2 + e^{i\pi}\varphi + \rho = \rho^3$$

or a quadratic in φ :

$$\varphi^2 + e^{i\pi}\varphi - 1 = 0$$

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